

Modelling equitable public transport infrastructure: pre-implementation accessibility assessment of Bogotá's metro system using synthetic GTFS

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Summary

This study evaluates the distributional accessibility impacts of Bogotá's planned metro Lines 1 and 2 across income groups. We developed synthetic GTFS datasets for the future metro system and employed R5R routing algorithms to model multimodal accessibility under current and future scenarios. Using cumulative opportunity measures, we quantified accessibility changes to employment and commercial opportunities. Results show that the overall median accessibility increases by 7.6% within 60-minute travel budgets, with greatest improvements concentrated in lower-income areas. Lower third- and fourth-income deciles experience accessibility gains approximately 50% greater than the highest decile, suggesting the infrastructure may reduce transport-related inequalities.

KEYWORDS: transport systems; spatial justice; accessibility; transport equity; urban planning

1. Introduction

Major public transport projects can reshape urban opportunity structures, yet traditional appraisal methodologies emphasise aggregate economic benefits often overlooking differential socio-economic impacts (Bills and Walker, 2017). This research examines Bogotá's forthcoming metro network through quantitative accessibility analysis, analysing how Lines 1 and 2 (commencing service in 2028 and 2034) will modify access to economic centres across income strata.

Latin American cities face distinctive challenges from rapid demographic expansion through informal settlement processes, generating pronounced socio-economic spatial fragmentation (Borsdorf, Hidalgo and Vidal-Koppmann, 2016; Oviedo et al., 2019). Disadvantaged communities typically occupy peripheral zones with insufficient infrastructure, whilst employment concentrates centrally, with residents needing transport connectivity most facing extensive distances, poor service, and disproportionate costs (Falavigna and Hernandez, 2016; Guzman, Oviedo and Cardona, 2018).

Bogotá exemplifies these dynamics. Over three decades, population has approached 8 million, showing polarisation: affluence northward, deprivation southward and south-westward (Guzman, Oviedo and Bocarejo, 2017). The TransMilenio BRT, inaugurated in 2000, accommodates 36% of journeys yet confronts capacity constraints and inadequate peripheral coverage (Hidalgo and Gutiérrez, 2013; Guzman and Cardona, 2021).

Whilst extensive research has examined TransMilenio's equity implications (Bocarejo S. and Oviedo H., 2012; Guzman and Oviedo, 2018), prior metro analyses used simplified assumptions rather than operational modelling. Our methodological contribution includes: i) generating complete GTFS datasets for non-operational infrastructure, ii) applying advanced routing methods to replicate

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multimodal travel sequences, and iii) systematically measuring distributional effects across income categories using fine-grained spatial data.

2. Methodology

2.1. Data

Our framework uses multiple data sources including transport networks, economic activity distributions, and demographic characteristics. Existing BRT operations are characterised through GTFS specifications (Transmilenio S.A., 2023) documenting service patterns including route configurations, stopping points, service intervals, and journey durations. Pedestrian networks derive from OpenStreetMap, establishing the foundational connectivity structure for non-transit movement. Bogotá benefits from relatively comprehensive OSM coverage, consistently ranking among the most thoroughly mapped Latin American cities owing to sustained contributions from local and international mapping communities. Planned metro infrastructure is represented via municipal spatial datasets from Bogotá's City Council. Economic activity patterns are captured through land use classifications (Alcaldía de Bogotá D.C., 2022) identifying commercial and employment concentrations across the metropolitan area. Household economic status is established through Multipurpose Survey microdata (Secretaría Distrital de Planeación and DANE, 2023) containing individual-level income and demographic records. WorldPop population density estimates enable population-weighted accessibility calculations. To harmonise the different data sets (at different spatial resolutions), we use a hexagonal grid at resolution 9, corresponding to analysis units of 0.105 km² area.

Given the non-operational status of the metro network, we constructed synthetic GTFS representations for both planned lines conforming to official specification standards. Our generation procedure utilises published alignment geometry, station coordinate data, and projected operational characteristics including anticipated average operating velocity of approximately 43 km/h (Metro de Bogotá, 2022). Service frequency parameters reflect differential headway assumptions: three-minute intervals during morning (6:30–9:00) and evening (16:00–19:00) peak periods, extending to fifteen-minute intervals throughout off-peak operations (Alcaldía de Bogotá D.C., 2019).

2.2. Accessibility computation framework

We measure accessibility through cumulative opportunity counts implemented via the R5R computational package (Pereira and Herszenhut, 2023). From each origin hexagon, we count accessible opportunities under three temporal budget configurations: 30-, 60-, and 90-minute total journey durations coupled with corresponding maximum pedestrian components of 15, 30, and 30 minutes respectively. These threshold selections reflect empirical travel behaviour patterns documented in municipal mobility surveys indicating substantial trip duration clustering around 60-minute thresholds (Alcaldía de Bogotá D.C., 2019). Opportunity destinations comprise employment locations identified through commercial corridor designations within land use classifications.

The computational sequence comprises four stages: i) constructing integrated multimodal network representations from GTFS transit specifications and OpenStreetMap infrastructure data; ii) calculating complete origin-destination impedance matrices across all hexagonal cell pairs; iii) filtering destination sets based on specified temporal impedance thresholds; iv) aggregating opportunity counts within feasible destination sets to generate location-specific accessibility scores. Resulting accessibility distributions are subsequently classified by household income deciles, enabling systematic evaluation of equity outcomes across economic strata.

We model three scenarios: "Baseline" characterises current accessibility via pedestrian movement and existing BRT services; "Y2030" incorporates Metro Line 1 operation alongside continuing BRT provision; "Y2035" represents full system implementation including both metro lines. All computational runs simulate peak period conditions reflecting maximum service provision. Our models

assume schedule adherence as specified in GTFS timetables for both existing BRT and planned metro services. In practice, TransMilenio experiences significant operational variability due to overcrowding and mixed-traffic running on certain trunk corridors (Vélez et al, 2014), meaning that realised accessibility under baseline conditions may be lower than modelled. Conversely, the segregated right-of-way and automated signalling planned for the metro may support higher schedule reliability than BRT, though this remains to be validated operationally. Our results should therefore be interpreted as reflecting planned rather than realised service levels.

Figure 1 a) Distribution of employment opportunities. b) Population and income distributions in Bogotá

3. Results

Aggregate accessibility metrics indicate that full metro implementation will increase median opportunity reach within 30-minute budgets by 1.2%, within 60-minute budgets by 7.6%, and within 90-minute budgets by 0.9% by 2035. The maximum impact is found for journeys between 30 and 60 minutes, with attenuated effects for 90-minute threshold trips. This pattern suggests that extended travel budgets already permit access to most metropolitan opportunities under baseline conditions, whilst metro provision enables faster trips for reaching these destinations rather than expanding destination choice sets.

Figure 2 Geographical distributions of accessibility change per income level across temporal threshold specifications

Figure 2 shows the spatial distribution of accessibility changes across different income levels. Accessibility improvements seem to benefit lower-income populations across all scenario and threshold configurations, with particular benefits for the lower third- and fourth-income deciles (**Figure 3**). Under 60-minute thresholds, both Y2030 and Y2035 scenarios show improvements between the lower second and seventh deciles when incorporating metro services, with peak gains corresponding to the lower third and fourth deciles. Comparative analysis between extreme income deciles under 60-minute threshold reveals that the first and second decile populations (i.e. lower incomes) experience superior accessibility gains relative to ninth and tenth deciles. Quantitatively, third and fourth decile households realise median accessibility improvements exceeding those of the highest decile by 43.8% and 58.1% respectively.

Figure 3 Disaggregated accessibility change distributions by income decile across scenarios

4. Conclusion

This research establishes that Bogotá's planned metro infrastructure has the potential to focus accessibility benefits toward lower-income populations occupying western and southwestern metropolitan zones (like Bosa and San Cristóbal). Our findings suggest that Bogotá's metro implementation may attenuate transport-related inequality, contrasting with evidence from other metropolitan contexts where major infrastructure investments have predominantly advantaged affluent populations (Delmelle and Casas, 2012; Foth, Manaugh and El-Geneidy, 2013). However, realising equitable outcomes likely requires complementary policy interventions encompassing affordable fare structures, seamless integration with existing BRT operations, and mechanisms preventing gentrification-induced residential displacement within zones experiencing greatest accessibility enhancement.

At the time of writing, official fare levels for the metro have not been confirmed, though integration with Bogotá's existing unified fare collection system (TuLlave) has been indicated. Given that transport expenditure already represents a disproportionate burden for lower-income households in Bogotá (Guzman and Oviedo, 2018), the accessibility gains identified here could be substantially negated if metro fares introduce a premium above current BRT tariffs.

Some technical limitations worth to be acknowledged include our cumulative opportunity measure treating all destinations as equally valuable regardless of employment type or quality, and not accounting for competition effects whereby multiple workers may seek the same opportunities. Also, the hexagonal aggregation, whilst providing consistent spatial units, may smooth localised accessibility variations. Furthermore, the analysis captures a static snapshot of land use patterns and does not model induced changes in employment location or residential sorting that metro provision may catalyse over time.

Future investigations should examine how accessibility improvements translate into actual travel behaviour modifications and whether enhanced accessibility generates tangible economic advancement for lower-income populations. Applying this methodological framework to other Latin American metropolitan areas planning major transit investments would enable comparative analysis examining how divergent urban contexts and routing decisions influence distributional outcomes.

The accessibility impacts demonstrated here suggest that careful infrastructure planning incorporating explicit equity objectives can generate transport investments that meaningfully address urban

inequality.

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